

OPEN LETTER

Creating circular industrial symbiosis for end-of-life wind turbine blades from wind power and construction value chains

[version 1; peer review: awaiting peer review]

Ana T Lima ¹, Ashal Tyurkay¹, Javier Romero-Gil¹, Charilaos Paraskevoulakos¹, Tao Liu ¹, Søren Fæster², Leon Mishnaevsky Jr², Maria Korsali³, Duc Tung Dao⁴, Victor Pacheco⁵, Genís Colomino⁶, Florent Gauvin⁷, Nataliya Lushnikovah⁷, Kristen Skelton⁸, Morten Philipsend⁹, Amaia Gómez¹⁰, H. Giray Resat¹¹, Thomas Matschei¹², Anya Vollpracht¹², Cynthia Morales Cruz¹², Maria Modestou¹³, Dionisis Semitekolos¹³, Costas Charitidis ¹³

¹Department of Environmental and Resource Engineering, Technical University of Denmark, Kgs Lyngby, Capital Region of Denmark, 2800, Denmark

²Department of Wind and Energy Systems, Technical University of Denmark, Roskilde, Region Zealand, DK-4000, Denmark

³Global Consulting Sustainability AS, Global Consulting Sustainability AS, Drammen, 3024, Norway

⁴Holcim Innovation Center, Saint Quentin Fallavier-Lyon, France

⁵Holcim Stiftung zur Forderung der wissenschaftlichen Fortbildung, Holderbank, Aargau, 6300, Switzerland

⁶Department of Engineering, Projects and Innovation,, Prezero, Barcelona, Spain

⁷University of Technology Eindhoven Department of Built Environment, Eindhoven, North Brabant, The Netherlands

⁸GE Renewable Energy, GE Vernova, Aalborg, Denmark

⁹LM wind Power, Kolding, Denmark

¹⁰Technological Division, Acciona Construction Business, Madrid, Spain

¹¹Renao Global Consulting, ANKARA, Turkey

¹²RWTH Aachen University Faculty of Civil Engineering, Aachen, North Rhine-Westphalia, Germany

¹³Research Lab of Advanced, Composite, Nano-Materials and Nanotechnology (R-NanoLab), School of Chemical Engineering,, National Technical University of Athens, 9 Heroon Polytechniou,, Athens, Attica, GR-15773, Greece

V1 First published: 10 Mar 2026, 6:68
<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.22681.1>

Latest published: 10 Mar 2026, 6:68
<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.22681.1>

Open Peer Review

Approval Status AWAITING PEER REVIEW

Any reports and responses or comments on the article can be found at the end of the article.

Abstract

The upcoming scarcity of certain mineral resources in the construction industry has been known for years, with some warning that extractable ores may be exhausted within several decades. ¹ Although this has been accepted for scarcer elements such as molybdenum or zinc, the scarcity of preconceived “abundant” resources such as sand or gravel is difficult to acknowledge. Nevertheless, recent studies have highlighted this scarcity at the local scale and connected it to its intense use by the construction industry as an aggregate. ^{2,2} The construction industry is the sink for a large fraction of mineral

resources extracted (e.g.,³) and therefore should also lead the way in reducing the use of virgin materials while also finding ways to recirculate waste materials.

Keywords

Construction materials, Wind power, Circular economy, Recycling, Repurpose, Repair, Reuse, end-of-life, wind turbine blades, value chain partnerships

This article is included in the [Horizon Europe gateway](#).

Corresponding author: Ana T Lima (atmli@dtu.dk)

Author roles: **Lima AT:** Conceptualization, Data Curation, Funding Acquisition, Project Administration, Writing – Original Draft Preparation, Writing – Review & Editing; **Tyurkay A:** Writing – Review & Editing; **Romero-Gil J:** Writing – Review & Editing; **Paraskevoulakos C:** Writing – Review & Editing; **Liu T:** Writing – Review & Editing; **Fæster S:** Writing – Review & Editing; **Mishnaevsky Jr L:** Writing – Review & Editing; **Korsali M:** Visualization, Writing – Review & Editing; **Tung Dao D:** Writing – Review & Editing; **Pacheco V:** Conceptualization, Writing – Review & Editing; **Colomino G:** Writing – Review & Editing; **Gauvin F:** Writing – Review & Editing; **Lushnikovah N:** Writing – Review & Editing; **Skelton K:** Writing – Review & Editing; **Philipsend M:** Writing – Review & Editing; **Gómez A:** Writing – Review & Editing; **Resat HG:** Writing – Review & Editing; **Matschei T:** Writing – Review & Editing; **Vollpracht A:** Writing – Review & Editing; **Morales Cruz C:** Writing – Review & Editing; **Modestou M:** Writing – Review & Editing; **Semitekolos D:** Writing – Review & Editing; **Charitidis C:** Writing – Review & Editing

Competing interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Grant information: This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No. 101096437

The funders had no role in study design, data collection and analysis, decision to publish, or preparation of the manuscript.

Copyright: © 2026 Lima AT *et al.* This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

How to cite this article: Lima AT, Tyurkay A, Romero-Gil J *et al.* **Creating circular industrial symbiosis for end-of-life wind turbine blades from wind power and construction value chains [version 1; peer review: awaiting peer review]** Open Research Europe 2026, 6:68 <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.22681.1>

First published: 10 Mar 2026, 6:68 <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.22681.1>

Simultaneously, the wind power industry must address the increasing stream of end-of-life (EoL) wind turbine blades, whose primary materials are fiber-reinforced plastics (FRP). Europe’s wind energy generation is expected to expand from 200 GW to 2,300 GW in the coming 30 years⁴ by using larger and more resistant blade structures (the capacity of wind turbines will increase from 5–10 MW to over 25 MW). With repowering, there are a considerable number of EoL wind turbine blades. Despite various existing technologies for recycling composites, these solutions are not available at an industrial scale or economically competitive, with cement co-processing and landfills being the most widely used methods today. An estimated total–40-60,000 tons of wind turbines are likely to be decommissioned in Europe by the end of 2023, with an expected increase to 325,000 tons by 2050.⁵ Waste management has become a key priority in the wind industry with the increasing number of wind turbines that come to the end of their operating lifetime.⁶

Circular economy across 2 value chains

Circular Economy (CE) has been proposed as a material and energy-efficient solution for product value chains (e.g., the Ellen MacArthur Foundation). The concept has gained considerable momentum in recent decades and has been adopted across sectors and disciplines. The current accepted framework establishes (from high to low circularity) Refuse, Rethink, Reduce, Reuse, Repair, Refurbish, Remanufacture, Repurpose, Recycle, and Recover. We reduce and optimize resource and material use as we increase the circularity ladder. In summary, reuse is more energy-, material-, and resource-efficient than recycling. The success of the R framework resides in its versatility in cross-sectoral applications, with numerous products and applications fitting the CE concept.

Composite recycling is a cross-sector challenge, and cross-value chain cooperation is imperative for closing the loop of EoL wind turbine blades. By bringing the wind energy and construction value chains together, we aim to create a symbiotic relationship that avoids sending EoL wind turbine blades to landfills by using them as a secondary resource in the construction industry, thereby reducing its dependency on raw virgin resource materials such as reactive binders and fine aggregates, such as siliceous sand or fillers.⁷ This is precisely what the project Blades2Build aims to support in achieving the EU’s 2050 Environmental Goals and Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Blades2Build is a new Horizon Europe Innovation project that demonstrates at an industrial scale the ambitious goal of improving and supporting circularity solutions for EoL wind blades by exploring three different circular stages (Figure 1):

- Direct reuse of EoL wind turbine blades with minimal refurbishment or processing.

Figure 1. The circular options put forward by Blades2Build to simultaneously reduce waste from wind power generation and pressure on raw materials by the construction industry.

- Individual material constituents of the blades (and wind turbine blade manufacturing waste) are repurposed for other uses/products, specifically in construction materials, with the use of concrete and asphalt mixtures as the first option, creating circular products.
- Recycling the blade and manufacturing waste containing resin in cement/clinker co-processing as alternative raw materials and fuel (the resin provides heat, while the fibers left after combustion can be used as raw materials).

From the repurposing and recycling routes, we will create new construction materials with FRP material waste from wind turbine blade structures.

Synergistic and multidisciplinary approaches are required to achieve a truly circular future. We cannot neglect that our society stands on “raw” materials exploitation and manufacturing, and that many products and services need these materials’ conditions to function. As we strive for higher levels of circularity (reuse, reduce), we should cooperate with cross-value chains – in an open-loop supply chain fashion – to use waste materials from one value chain and relieve the pressure on raw materials of the other in an economical process. In this way, we guarantee that the future renewable energy supply and construction materials respond to policies that are responsible for zero waste and resource efficiency.

Authors’ statement

The first author wrote the manuscript. The co-authors were equal collaborators in editing and revising this article.

Ethics and consent

Ethical approval and consent were not required.

Disclaimer

The information on this publication is for general informational purposes only. The European Commission makes no representations or warranties of any kind, express or implied, about the completeness, accuracy, reliability, suitability, or availability with respect to the publication or the information, products, services, or related graphics contained on the publication for any purpose.

Data availability

No data was used in the writing of this statement paper – data used in this paper are from external references. All references are cited in the reference list.

References

1. Henckens MLCM, van Ierland EC, Driessen PJJ, *et al.*: **Mineral resources: Geological scarcity, market price trends, and future generations.** *Res. Policy.* 2016; **49**: 102–111. [Publisher Full Text](#)
2. Ioannidou D, Meylan G, Sonnemann G, *et al.*: **Is gravel becoming scarce? Evaluating the local criticality of construction aggregates.** *Resour. Conserv. Recycl.* 2017; **126**: 25–33. [Publisher Full Text](#)
3. European Commission: **Buildings and construction - Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship and SMEs.** 2026. (accessed February 3, 2026). [Reference Source](#)
4. Dickson G: **Electrifying Europe with wind energy – towards net-zero by 2050 - The European Files, The European Files.** 2021. (accessed March 23, 2023). [Reference Source](#)
5. Lichtenegger G, Rentizelas AA, Trivyza N, *et al.*: **Offshore and onshore wind turbine blade waste material forecast at a regional level in Europe until 2050.** *Waste Manag.* 2020; **106**: 120–131. [PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
6. WindEurope: **How to build a circular economy for wind turbine blades through policy and partnerships.** WindEurope, Wind Europe; 2021. (accessed March 23, 2023). [Reference Source](#)
7. Liu T, Duyal C, Paraskevoulakos C, *et al.*: **Effect of wind turbine blade waste on cement hydration and gel structure: Competitive interaction of glass and polyester resin.** *Compos. Part B Eng.* 2026; **311**: 113273. [Publisher Full Text](#)